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EFFECT OF PATIENT EDUCATION ON MEDICATION ADHERENCE BEHAVIOUR IN MIGRAINE PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Migraine poses recognizable burden on the individuals suffering from this disorder in terms of impaired quality of life and financial costs. It was found that adequate education helps the patient to understand the importance of medication adherence to achieve the desired therapeutic goals. Aim: The main aim of the study was to improve the overall quality of life of migraine patients by providing proper education regarding medication adherence. Objective: The main objective of the study was to assess the effect of patient education on improving medication adherence behavior in migraine patients. Method: This study was a prospective randomized study conducted over a period of 9 months at the outpatient department of Neurology, JSS Medical College Hospital, Mysore which is a multispecialty tertiary care teaching hospital. Education regarding disease, medication, diet, and lifestyle modification was provided at baseline visit and at each follow-up visit to the test group patients. The control group patients received detailed education only at the final follow-up visit. Patient's medication adherence was assessed in each follow up visits with the help of Morisky's Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS). Difference in the scoring at the time of first, second and third follow up visits was compared and the difference in percentage was calculated. Results: A total of 190 patients were enrolled in the study. Out of which 168 completed all the study follow ups. The main outcome of our study was a significant increase in the MMAS score of the test patients (educated patients) from follow up 1 to follow up 3. The mean scores of the medication adherence in the control patients were not consistent in the follow ups. Conclusion: This study concluded that patient education has a significant role in improving medication adherence in patients with migraine. This study provides an overview of adherence behavior in migraine patients and the significance of educating patients for improving medication adherence behavior and thereby improving the overall quality of life in migraine patients.

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INTRODUCTION

Patient's adherence to the prescribed medications is one of the most important issues in the medical treatment of chronic illnesses. Adherence is the degree to which a person's behavior coincides with medical advice.^[1] Adherence to prescribed medicines is a way to improve health, assuming the prescription is appropriate and correct.^[2] According to WHO, non-adherence to medications is a "worldwide problem of striking magnitude?" Poor medication adherence can cause negative health outcomes such as worsening disease or even death.^[3] Poor medication adherence also may result in increased health care cost. There are 33%-69% of drug-related hospital admissions in US are because of poor medication adherence, along with a cost of about \$100 billion a year.^[4] In our study the objective was to assess the significance of patient education in enhancing medication adherence behavior in migraine patients. It was also known from various studies that a proper medication adherence is one of the major contributing factor in improving quality of life in chronic illness. International Headache Society describes migraine as idiopathic, recurrent headache disorder manifesting in attacks lasting 4 to 72 hours. Typical characteristics of migraine include unilateral location, pulsating quality, moderate to severe intensity and aggravation by triggering factors such as high temperature, noise pollution and frequent fasting. Patients with migraine also reported with nausea, vomiting, photophobia and phonophobia.^[5,6] The prevalence of migraine increases until the fourth decade and then decreases with increasing age. Many population based studies have revealed that the prevalence of migraine is higher in females than males.^[7,8] Migraine poses recognizable burden on the individuals suffering from this disorder in terms of personal suffering, impaired quality of life (QoL) and financial costs. Recurrent attacks often trigger fear in the mind of the sufferer and damage the family life, the social life and the professional life.^[9] Adequate education helps the patient to understand the importance of medication adherence to achieve the desired therapeutic goals. Strict adherence to the medication helps in maintaining the adequate concentration of medication in the plasma and achieving the desired therapeutic goals. Studies show that patients having problems in communicating with their doctors were much more likely to underuse or overuse medications and hence leading to non adherence.^[10] During the patient counseling the counselor can identify the possible reasons for non-adherence and help the patients to overcome the non adherence. Hence the aim of our study was to assess the effect of patient education on improving medication adherence behavior in the patients with migraine

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study design and period:

This study was a prospective randomized study conducted over a period of 9 months.

Study site:

The study was conducted at the outpatient department of Neurology, JSS Medical College Hospital, Mysore which is a multispecialty tertiary care teaching hospital.

Study Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Adult patients of either sex with a diagnosis of migraine visiting neurology OPD
- Patients who are able to read, write and understand working Kannada or English language or those able to get support from the attendants
- Patients willing to give written informed consent

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients below 18 years
- Secondary headache
- Status migrainicus
- Non co-operative patients
- Patients with other co morbidities

Ethics Approval:

The ethical approval of the study was granted by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee, JSS College of Pharmacy, Mysore 15.

Sources of data:

All relevant and necessary data were collected from the patient's prescriptions, interviews with patients and/ or their care takers and documented in a suitably designed data collection form. The collected data includes patient's demographics, alcohol and smoking history, educational level, past medical history and patient known allergies.

Designing of data collection form:

A suitable data collection form was designed for use in the study. The following data were collected for the patients enrolled in the study.

- Patient's demographic details, educational status, social habits, socio economic condition
- Past medical history
- Patients known allergies to food and drugs
- Characteristics and triggering factors for migraine

- Medication adherence behavior by applying Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS)

Preparation of education materials:

A patient information leaflet which explains about signs, symptoms, triggering factors, pharmacological and non pharmacological management plan and life style modifications to be taken about migraine was prepared in the local language for providing to the patients. Also a patient diary which records the headache frequency, duration and triggers (cause for headache for individual patient) was prepared and provided to all patients.

Study Procedure:

Patient's meeting the study criteria were enrolled in the study after explaining about the study and obtained their written informed consent. Patients were randomized into control and test by using simple randomization technique. At the enrolment data pertaining to demographics, educational level, socio economic status, past medical history, alcohol and smoking history were collected. Patient's diary was provided to all patients at the baseline visit in order to record their headache frequency, duration and triggers of their headache. Structured patient education including patient information leaflet (PIL) was provided to all test group patients at the baseline visit. The control group patients received education only at the final follow up visit.

Medication adherence:

Patient's medication adherence was assessed with the help of four item Morisky's Medication Adherence scale (MMAS). This scale consists of four questions. Patients answered four questions and each 'YES' answer scored zero points and each 'NO' answer scored one point. The patients who scored a total of 3 and 4 were categorized as having high adherence, those scored 1 and 2 were categorized as having medium adherence and those scored zero point was categorized as having low adherence. The medication adherence scoring was done at the time of follow up visits and patients were categorized as patients with high non adherence, medium non adherence and high adherence. Difference in scoring at the time of first, second and third follow up visits was compared and the difference in percentage were calculated.

Statistical Analysis:

Results were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for windows version 16.0. Significance of change in the MMAS scores from baseline to final follow up was assessed using Repeated Measure ANOVAs. P values <0.05 is considered as significant.

RESULTS

A total of 190 patients were enrolled in the study. Out of which 168 completed all the study follow ups. The age and gender distribution of the enrolled patients are presented in the table 01 & table 02.

Table 01: Demographics (Age distribution):

Age	Group			Significance (P)
	Control (%)	Test (%)	Total (control+test) (%)	0.112
15-20	10 (11.4)	9 (11.3)	19 (11.3)	
21-30	44 (50)	31 (38.8)	75 (44.6)	
31-40	22 (25)	30 (37.5)	52 (31)	
41-50	12 (13.6)	7 (8.8)	19 (11.3)	
51 and above	0	3 (3.8)	3 (1.8)	

Table 02: Demographics (Gender distribution):

Sex	Control (%)	Test (%)	Total (control+test) (%)	0.209
Male	31 (35.2)	21 (26.3)	52 (31)	
Female	57 (64.8)	59 (73.8)	116 (69)	
Total (n)	88 (100)	80 (100)	168 (100)	

The mean age of the enrolled patients was 30.95 years. In the study majority of the patients were from the age group of 21-30 (44.6%) followed by 31-40 (31%). The female predominance was more than two fold greater than the males (31%) in the study population. There was no statistically significant difference found between the age and genders of the enrolled patients ($p>0.05$) The educational details of the enrolled patients were shown in the table 03.

Table 03: Educational details of enrolled patients:

	Control (%)	Test (%)	Total (n) (%)
Illiterate	19 (21.6)	12 (15)	31 (18.4)
Primary School	27 (30.6)	27 (33.7)	54 (32.1)
Secondary School	20 (22.7)	13 (16.2)	33 (19.6)
Pre university	11 (12.5)	16 (20)	27 (16)
University	11 (12.5)	12 (15)	23 (13.7)

Influence of patient education on medication adherence behavior of migraine patients**Table 04: Influence of education on MMAS score.**

GROUPS	VISITS						SIGNIFICANCE P =0.000
	Follow up-1		Follow up-2		Follow up-3		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Control	3.24	0.844	3.02	1.01	3.04	1.03	
Test	3.45	0.73	3.57	0.65	3.91	0.34	
Overall	3.35	0.8	3.28	0.90	3.45	0.89	

Figure 01: Graph showing correlation between patient education and MMAS score.

It was found that there was a significant increase in the MAQ score of the test patients (educated patients) from follow up 1 to follow up 3. The mean scores of the medication adherence in the control patients were not consistent in the follow ups.

DISCUSSION

Many studies suggested that pharmacists can play an important role by providing the counseling, which has shown a positive impact on health care and decrease the mortality and morbidity. A total of 190 patients were enrolled in the study during a period of 9 months. Out of which 168 patients completed all the study follow ups and 22 patients were considered as lost to follow up due to the missed visits. The reasons for the missed follow ups were improved health condition, transportation expenses, female patients had to depend their husbands to accompany them, lack of time for people who are working or unable to get leave from work. Out of 168 patients 80 patients belong to test group and 88 belong to control group. There was no significant difference observed between the age and gender of the enrolled patients. In our study female patients accounts for 69% of the total study population. In many studies conducted overseas found that a predominance of female gender over the male gender. In a study conducted by Richard B Lipton et al the prevalence of migraine among females was found to be 18.2% and that in males were 6.5%. In another study by M Roncolato et al the prevalence of migraine was found to be higher in women than men irrespective of the age range. This predominance can be attributed to the hormonally driven changes in females. In the present study majority of patients were in the age range of 21-30(44.6%) followed by 31-40 (31%). The reasons may be attributed to high stress and tension during that age. This finding was found to be comparable with earlier studies findings. In a study conducted by Ulku B et al, the prevalence of migraine was found to be high in women of reproductive age group. It is also reported in the global burden of disease (GBD) 2000 study that the prevalence of migraine is highest during the peak productive years (between the ages of 25-55 years).^[8] This results support our study findings where we found that the majority of patients were in the age range of 21-40 years.

The mean MMAS value of test group patients were increased from follow up 1 to follow up3 significantly at a $P < 0.05$ whereas the mean score of the MMAS of the control group were decreased from first to second follow up which then increased slightly in the third follow up. There was no significant difference found in the scores with the educational status and employment status of the patients.

CONCLUSION

This study provides an overview of medication adherence behavior in migraine patients and could also serve as a basis for further research. Our results imply that there was a significant increase in the medication adherence behavior of the educated patients compared to the control group patients. This study also concluded that a significant reduction in the migraine frequency and severity was observed in the test group patients compared to the control group patients. This reduction is mainly due to the education and support by the pharmacist

BOTTOM LINE

It is the duty of a clinical pharmacist to keep an eye over patient's medication adherence behavior especially in case of chronic diseases like migraine as medication adherence always acts as a key factor for improving quality of life in migraine patients. This study emphasizes that the pharmacist can play an important role in patient education and in the effective management of migraine. Thus future studies can be directed towards the various techniques to enhance medication adherence in migraine patients and its implementation through patient education.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

Authors are not having any conflicts of interest to declare.

ABBREVIATIONS:

MMAS : Morisky's Medication Adherence Scale
WHO : World Health Organization
QoL : Quality of Life
OPD : Out Patient Department
PIL : Patient Information Leaflet
GBD : Global burden of disease

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